

MANAGEMENT OF DUSTA VRANA WITH SKIN GRAFT- A CASE STUDY

¹*Dr. Pankaj Kumar Barman, ²Dr. Mustafizur Rahman

¹Prof. and Head, Department of Shalya Tantra, Govt. Ayurvedic College and Hospital
Guwahati-14.

²PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Govt. Ayurvedic College and Hospital Guwahati-
14.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Pankaj Kumar Barman

Prof. and Head, Department of Shalya
Tantra, Govt. Ayurvedic College and
Hospital Guwahati-14.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Discontinuation of the covering epithelium of skin or mucous membrane is called as ulcer which is described as Vrana in Ayurveda. The healing of the ulcer is a physiological response of the body. When a person does not maintain the proper treatment regimen, hygiene, along with indulgence of apathya ahar vihar and the wound contaminated with various micro organisms, converted to Dusta Vrana or non healing ulcer. Vrana Sandhan karma is known as repair and reconstructive surgery for wound which includes primary repair and skin grafting. In this study this principle of sushrut samhita for vran chikitcha applied. **Aim of the Study:** Management of dusta vran with skin graft. **Material & Method:** A 45 years non diabetic male patient had had been selected from OPD sufferings from non healing wound over medial malleous of left foot associated with pain and serous Discharge since 2

months. The wound was debrided after proper investigation. The edges were excited. After observing healthy granulation tissue the wound covered with partial thickness autografts taken from antero medial aspect of left thigh and dressing done. **Result:** wound healed completely without any complications with a proper functional skin. **Discussion:** This case report proved that non healing wound can be managed by proper vrana sodhan (wound debridement) and vrana ropana (wound bed preparation) along with partial thickness Skin

graft without any contracture. **Summary & Conclusion:** Skin graft has good effect in management of Dusta vran.

KEYWORDS: Dusta vrana, sandhan karma, skin graft, plastic surgery.

INRODUCTION

Ayurveda has eight branches. Surgery is one of the important branches of Ayurveda. Arcaharya Sushruta the ancient Indian Surgeon is recognized as the father of plastic surgery. Sushruta made an important contribution to the field of plastic and cataract surgery. Sushruta was the first surgeon who performed Nasa, Karna sandhan, Oshtasandhan also known Skin grafting, which is one of the most common surgical procedure in the area of non healing wound or ulcer by which skin or skin substitute is placed over a wound to replace and regenerate damaged tissue Grafts are typically described in terms of thickness or depth. A skin grafting is an effective way to controlled the progression of wound and prevention of infection. It improves the way of wound healing also prevent unsightly scar , contraction and also reduce loss of function due to improper healing. So, skin grafting decision was taken under local anesthesia to improve healing and prevention of infection.

CASE STUDY REPORT

A 45 years non diabetic male patient had been selected from OPD suffering from non healing wound over medial malleous of left foot associated with pain and serous discharge since 2 months. The wound was debrided after proper investigation. The edges were excited. After observing healthy granulation tissue the wound covered with partial thickness autografts taken from antero medial aspect of left thigh and dressing done.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

To study the effect of skin Graft in the management of non healing wound.

TYPE OF STUDY: Observational single case study without control group.

STUDY CENTER: Govt. Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Guwahati-14

STUDY DETAILS: Age-45yrs Occupation–Teacher Gender-Male Religion-Hindu Diet-Non Veg.

CHIEF COMPLAINTS: Non healing wound over medial malleous of left foot associated with pain since 2 months Occasional serous discharge Difficulty during walking **History of present illness** -Patient had an accidental injury 2 month back over medial malleous of left

foot associated with pain and Occasional serous discharge and difficulty during walking. The wound was treated with antibiotics ointment by a local doctor but wound healing was slow. So The patient came to GACH Shalya OPD had undergone treatment for Dushta varna, on a daily basis. **Past history** - There was no history of HTN, DM, Tuberculosis, or any other major systemic disorder.

ON EXAMINATION: No other systemic disorder found. Local Examination temperature Present. Tenderness Present. Pus discharge Present Non healing wound over medial malleous of left foot. Wound size-5x4x2cm. Shape-Round Margins- Regular BP-130/84mmhg.

LAB REPORTS -Hb-10gm, BT-2min30sec, BSL[R]-110mg, Sr.Creat-0.9mg/dl, Wbc-6100cmm. CT-4min 450sec. Sr.Urea-29mg/dl.Plt-257000cmm.

Diagnosis-Non healing wound.

According to Ayurveda: Drushta Vrana.

Treatment Plan: The wound was cleaned with Triphala Kwath daily, after proper cleaning with sterile swabs, and the dressing was done by applying Jatyadi taila with sterile gauze and bandage once daily. Lekhana karma was done for removing the slough from the wound. Lekhana was done for the wound to attain Shudha awastha, laskshana of jiwahatalabo, Mridu, snigdha and Shalkshana are seen. After the wound attains Shudha awastha, Ropana kriya is started. A large wound management decision was taken for Sandhana karma (Skin Grafting).

PROCEDURE

Local Anesthesia given under all AAP Painting and drapping done Split thickness autograft obtained from left thigh region by HUMBY'S Knife and placed in normal saline until it is to be used. Gauze pieces are placed over donor site to reduce blood loss and bandaging done Scrapping over actual wound are adone by sephalika patra and covered with obtained autograft Dressing done Patient had given IV antibiotic post operatively 3 days. Then oral antibiotics and analgesics for next 7days.After two consecutive days Cleaning and Dressing done.

Treatment outcome

Cleaning wound Triphala Kwath daily, dressing was done by applying Jatyadi taila with sterile gauze and bandage once daily. Lekhana karma was done for removing the slough from the wound. Sandhan karma was done for minimizing the time for wound healing.

Before Sandhan Karma

During Sandhan Karma

After Sandhan Karma

DISCUSSION

Acharya Sushruta has described plastic surgery. In plastic surgery Nasa-Sandhana (Rhinoplasty) Karna Sandhana (Auroplasty), and Oshta-Sandhana (lipoplasty) are mentioned in Ayurveda. The contribution of ancient Indian surgery in the field of plastic surgery is beyond imagination. During wars Pandu's punishment of cutting the nose or ear was considered in ancient times. Indian surgeon has applied their injurious technique for correcting Most modern principles of Plastic surgery resemble the origin of Acharya Sushruta's context. Principles of Plastic Surgery, (A) Skin Incision and Excision (B) Role of debridement and Irrigation (C) Role of suturing techniques (D) Management of large wound.

CONCLUSION

Acharya Sushruta has explained Shashti Upakrama for the management of Dushta vrana. Lekhana Karma is one of the Ashtavidha Shastrakarma explained in Shashti Upakrama marks the Pradhana Karma in the management of Vrana. Shashti Upakrama plays a significant role in converting Dushtavrana to Shuddha Avastha and thereby helps in quick and better healing of the wound. Acharya Sushruta has explained in detail about the Sandhan karma hence here in the case of a large wound we can use Sandhan karma (Skin grafting for large wounds). There is a need for the Sandhan karma procedure combined with contemporary technology for further growth of Ayurvedic science. The role of Ayurvedic Shashti Upakrama with help of sandman karma (Skin Grafting) can be used as an ideal treatment protocol for the large wound. When we look at some of the references for large wound management, such as Reconstruction of the Nose, Reconstruction of the Ear, and Reconstruction of the Lips, we

can see that the methods described in Sushruta are pioneers in Modern Sciences as well, as these procedures are followed exactly as Sushruta described them. When it comes to nose reconstruction, Sushruta recommends taking grafts from the frontal area while keeping the blood supply intact. This method is being followed today. Sushruta also documented fourteen procedures for re-creating the ear, only a handful of which are still used by modern science. Now there is a need for the advancement of Ayurveda with its own basic principle of Sandhan karma (Plastic surgery).

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